

THE ROLE OF VISUAL PRINCIPLES IN THE FORMATION OF LINGUISTIC COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article describes the importance of forming the participation skills of primary school students. The reason for the frequent use of visuals in elementary grades is that the child's thinking is not yet fully formed and needs to rely on concrete images. The purpose of visualization is not to understand the things themselves, but to use them as a support in explaining the known material. Because, due to the child's age, he cannot master learning tasks on his own without relying on visual supports. The reason for this is that it is easier for a child to perceive a concrete image than an abstract image, and he relies on it. This feature is characteristic not only of the first grade, but of all elementary school students.*

Keywords: *formation of participation competence, competence, participation competence of primary school students*

Demonstrations are often used in primary school because the child's mind is not yet fully formed and needs to rely on real images. The purpose of illustration is not to explain things themselves, but to use them as a basis for explaining certain material. Because of the age of the child, he will not be able to master reading tasks on his own without relying on visual aids. This is because it is easier for a child to perceive a real image than an abstract image. This feature is common not only in the first grade, but also in all primary school students.

Demonstrations in the classroom do not always work, so it is better to combine the oral interpretation of the content of the study with the demonstrations, alternating one to another. If the teacher is constantly presenting the lesson material orally, then due to the strong excitation of a certain center of the student's brain, it becomes slower and faster. And if the content of learning is constantly changing, both verbally and visually, then not only one giant of the brain, but also other centers will be added in turn, and students will be absent for a long time during the lesson.

The work on the formation of language and cultural competence of school children is carried out regularly in the Kazakh language and literature classes. One of the most important functions of visual aids for the formation of linguistic and cultural competence of primary school students is the use of certain language materials. One of the motivations for students to speak in the classroom is the picture, if the picture is made in accordance with aesthetic requirements, its theme and images correspond to the grammatical form and construction required by the program, it will be successful in shaping students' linguistic and cultural competence.

Distributed pictures are an effective form of visual aids for in-depth study of English language materials in accordance with these requirements, the formation of linguistic and cultural competence of students. This includes tasks related to the topic of the material, the image of the object or phenomenon, as well as the formation of skills to determine the meaning of a particular

word and its correct use, enriching the vocabulary of the student. The question in the picture may come not only from the vocabulary, but also from other areas of linguistics. For example, in Grade 4, during the exercise on the topic of “Verbs”, students are asked to reveal the meaning of the verbs “hear” and “be heard” in the picture, to make sentences involving the verbs in the dialogue of children talking on the phone. Such work allows to understand the meaning of words, to remember the rules of spelling, to check the level of mastery of the material, to develop the skills of communication in the presentation of the content of the given picture.

Video materials are one of the most effective visual aids in the formation of language and cultural competence of primary school students. Videos also consist of a set of visual materials. The main purpose of its use is to promote the development of language and cultural competence of primary school students, as well as the formation of literate writing skills, the formation of communicative speech. The content of each frame, which is given to students, requires accurate and accurate verbal description. Completion of this task will allow you to test your knowledge of the norms of literary language. Therefore, in order to reveal the content of each frame, the goal is to use the language materials mastered in connection with the object or phenomenon depicted in it.

For example, you can use the following frames when passing verb tenses.

1] A woman standing on the street with hand luggage looking at the driver from the cab window with a questioning look.

2] A bright-faced driver who opened the cab door and asked the woman to get in the car.

The teacher shows the shots one by one and asks one of the students to describe the course of action in the shots in the past tense and the other in the present tense. As a result, students gain a deeper understanding of the language material [verb tenses] through practical use, and learn to communicate systematically.

The use of visual aids in the classroom corresponds to the psychological basis for the formation of language and cultural competence of students, facilitates the development of long-term memory, as it allows you to systematically work with lexical material included in the active vocabulary.

Although lessons for the formation of language and cultural competence of primary school students can use visual aids for language development, these tools differ in content and purpose, as these visual aids are designed to develop other skills and abilities of the student. The main purpose of connecting speech is not only to write a summary and composition, but also to develop specific language skills, first of all to understand the topic and convey the main action and event in it in different genres [reporting, description, reasoning].

Vocabulary tools used to develop English speaking skills have their own characteristics. In fact, understanding the theme, the main idea of the work is not only through the content of the text, but also a combination of works of art and literature [reading, painting, graphics, film, etc.] that help to understand the main idea of the author. . The skills of compiling and organizing materials for a conversation are not only based on working with books, but also on the ability to perceive fragmentary images of works of art [drawings, sculptures] and to think about the collected material and systematically narrate what you see.

The ability to create in different genres in speech [expression] covers a wide range of logical operations that require different sources of knowledge in teaching.

The effectiveness of the descriptive work is closely linked with the formation of skills to determine the specifics of the object and the phenomenon described and to express their attitude to it, to determine the direction of the described activity. The development of these skills is facilitated by pictures, cartoons, storyboards [which allow you to reconsider the object or phenomenon described in words] and movies.

The skills of storytelling in the reporting genre are based on a set of skills, such as the ability to expand the plot scheme and the dynamics of action and story development, so it is useful to draw a story in the development of connecting speech.

The genre of commentary requires the development of skills to present theses, present compelling arguments and draw conclusions. Films, pictures, performances, etc. are used to educate students to express themselves. special function. However, in addition to textbooks in the native language and English, special language development films and films are needed to carry out the work at the appropriate level. Films that are easy for a young person to understand, that have an interesting story, and that evoke positive emotions in the viewer contribute to the development of communication skills.

Opinion building activities provide a great opportunity to develop coherent oral communication, as any student's response to any lesson is closer to genre feedback.

The correct formation of oral speech is associated with the acquisition of the ability to express the appropriate arguments, conclusions through intonation [rhythm of voice], as well as to gain the confidence of the interlocutor, while maintaining the politeness of the tone of voice. Sound recording [on tape] plays a big role in training this ability. Oral stories are important for the development of skills related to other genres. Audio recording helps students "listen" to the culmination of oral conversations. Understands how to convey the content of the story through the rhythm of the voice, the author's attitude to the object described in the story.

If the visual aids are closely related to the school curriculum, the methods tested by the best teachers and scholars, and the textbooks for English and mother tongue, they will have a positive effect on the development of coherent speech. This methodology identifies several stages in the formation of language skills, each stage offers several types of exercises in accordance with its purpose, in particular, model analysis, preparatory [analytical-synthetic] exercises and independent creative work. Visual aids are used at all stages of language development, but they have different functions depending on the purpose of each stage: they give a pattern of pronunciation or motivate its creation. Various visual aids can play the role of motivation. Sound recordings are also used as an example of connecting speech. If it is characterized not only by the inclusion of various compositional forms of oral expression [oral comment, description, narration], but also by the conveyance of various emotional states through open and clear oral speech, it performs this function to its own extent. During the preparation exercise, these teaching methods should facilitate the formation of certain skills and the acquisition of theoretical knowledge necessary for work with works of different compositional genres. It can use a variety of learning activities for this purpose, including audio and screen, but their content needs to be clarified. For example, any slide film does not always achieve its intended purpose, but only those that allow to determine the relationship between the main stages of the story in the construction of the plot.

Interactive whiteboards are widely used in schools to write summaries and essays. If the structure and content of the visuals are related to a specific type of creative work aimed at writing summaries, slides and movies serve as a stimulus to describe what you see. Any textbook used as a language stimulus should be age-appropriate in terms of clarity and structure of the author's thought[1], [2], [3], [4].

The use of visual aids that facilitate the creation of a natural need for communication during independent creative work [the final stage in the formation of linguistic and cultural competence of primary school students] is a prerequisite for the formation of linguistic and cultural competence of primary school students, especially oral language.

Each of the above activities has its own opportunities to motivate students to create their own pronunciation: if the speech has a clear and expressive rhythm of the voice, the picture and video give additional creative inspiration to the graphics: the combination of words and images.

Film is the most important tool for the formation of language and cultural competence of primary school students. Because there is a harmony between video and audio, the video is in action, and the audio is complemented by music. However, in the final stages of language development, visualization is needed to motivate [motivate] the desire to express what one has seen and heard and one's attitude to it, as well as to facilitate creative pursuits and facilitate it. In order to practice oral presentation, it is useful to use audio texts in the genre of short and interesting plot, open and clear voice rhythm. Oral narratives are composed in the genre of informative, in the text of the plot, which is not interrupted from the most interesting and decisive part of the story, using sound recordings that lead the listener to creative imagination. The content of the story should instruct the young author to develop a new version of the story line and complete it in a logical system. [For example, sad or happy is resolved].

The materials presented for the training of oral communication also vary depending on their specifics. At the initial stage, the preparatory exercises use successful or unsuccessful answers to questions about a particular action or event, the author's arguments to defend his point of view, the following notes. In order to encourage students to express their opinions, it is helpful to listen to notes that compare conflicting views on a particular event. Such recordings engage the audience in a debate, forcing them to determine the direction of the action under discussion, to side with a particular point of view.

Filmstrips for each stage of storytelling are different in content and structure. For the first training exercises it is better to use an interesting plot, which is perfect in terms of construction. Each frame is explained verbally, explaining the relationship between the stages of development of the action and the event: it facilitates the perception of the visual material as a whole.

In order to write a creative story in English, they use unfinished or full-plot, but subtitled films. Each of these options helps to improve the plot and explain it verbally, to reveal to young viewers their own creativity. Filmstrips that teach storytelling in a systematic way should be engaging and engaging in terms of content[5].

One of the motivations for students to talk is a movie. Its peculiarity is due to the plot structure and the ability of the protagonist to sound [speak] and the musical accompaniment[6], [7].

When using visual aids, the teacher should combine verbal descriptions of the object and phenomenon [or its image]. Because the visuals are definitely dumb. This sharing of feelings and words is a prerequisite for children to recognize the individual in general, the individual in general. The teacher not only introduces the features and details of the object, but also explains its features. A teacher's speech is more powerful than a visual aid, because it can fully cover the necessary details that the author of the illustration did not take into account.

To draw the conclusion, the purpose of the formation of linguistic and cultural competence of primary school students is the organization of research activities of students through cultural materials, increasing student engagement, the formation of skills for independent learning, development of creative and logical thinking, language and cultural competencies.

REFERENCES

1. N. Koryakovtseva Timeline of the organization of the organization of the study of a foreign language.: For teachers. - M: Arctic, 2002-65pp.
2. Nurakhmetov N.N. Role of new textbooks in the formation of competencies, scientific support for the implementation of secondary education for 12 years: Materials of the International Scientific and Practical Conference - Almaty, April 20-21, 2007. 39-45 b.
3. Arapova K.M. pedagogical conditions for organizing the self-fulfillment of students' work in the conditions of credit training. Dissertation prepared for doctoral dissertation on pedagogy, Almaty, 2008, 186
4. Rakitin E.A. Educational basis is a key combination in education. M., 2004. Iesova G.I. Methodology exclamation point of the system of the republican language in the Kazakh school A.A.
5. Farmer's A.V. scientific and educational aspects of communication education. Autoref. diss on sois.
6. Genghizova A.A. Communication - Integration Technologies Learning Russian As a Foreign Country at the University. Diss. Doc. pedd. Naughty. "Almaty, 2005. - 315c.
7. Thesis developed for his doctorate in the system of higher education institution Kenzhebekov B.T. dissertation Almaty, 2008, 140 b.